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Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

Health Metrics and Information Behavior: How Users Estimate and Use Self-Quantifying Activity and Health Information (Questionnaire)

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
	Introduction	<p>Dear participants,</p> <p>As an activity tracker enthusiast, I'm thrilled about the functionalities of those devices. Notably, it is fascinating that people get support not only to be more physically active but also to develop an awareness of their health and fitness through the activity trackers.</p> <p>I would like to investigate what (information) needs users of activity trackers, here Fitbit users, have, and which kind of information they are actually using. The survey also includes excerpts from the Fitbit application, which requires more accurate reading and alignment with the excerpts.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Thank you very much for participating and your support! Have fun!</p> <p>Kind regards, Aylin Ilhan (aylin[dot]ilhan[at]hhu[dot]de)</p>	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
1*	Exclusion criterion	<p>Before we start, the crucial question first: Do you use a Fitbit activity tracker?</p> <p>Important: <i>The sole mobile tracking with the Fitbit application is here not counted as a Fitbit activity tracker. It has to be a Fitbit device (wearable).</i></p>	<p>Yes-no question</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#2] • no [Finish survey]
<p><i>Great!</i></p> <p><i>First, I would like to ask some general questions related to workouts (frequency) and related to your Fitbit activity tracker (usage and wearing frequency) to identify possible differences.</i></p>			
2*	Exercise (frequency)	How often do you exercise (e.g., going to the gym, workouts at home, workouts outside, other sports, etc.)?	<p>I'm exercising</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • never • few times per year • every few months • once a month • several times per month • 1-2 times per week • 3 or more times per week • every day • I prefer not to say.
3*	Fitbit (usage frequency)	Since when have you been using your Fitbit activity tracker?	<p>Since:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • less than a week • 1-2 weeks • 3 weeks • a month • several months • a year • several years
4		<p>Did you use any other activity trackers before your Fitbit activity tracker?</p> <p>If so, I would be happy to receive more information, such as which device, how long you have been using it or are using it, etc.</p> <p><i>Otherwise, you can skip this page by clicking Next.</i></p>	[Free text field]
5*	Fitbit (wearing frequency)	How frequently do you wear your Fitbit activity tracker?	<p>Single selection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only while exercising • Only while sleeping • Only when I'm leaving the house • Throughout the whole day but not while sleeping • Throughout the whole day and night (including sleeping) • Irregularly • Other usage frequencies: [Free text field]

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Steps			
6*	Exclusion criterion	Are you consciously using the tracking of your steps with your Fitbit activity tracker? Consciously means here that you are deliberately looking at your Fitbit activity tracker/application.	Yes-no question • yes [#6.1] • no [#7]
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the tracking of the steps. This means I want to know why you are using the function.</i>			
6.1*	Steps (wristband/application) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at the count of my steps on my Fitbit tracker/application because I want to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
6.1.1*		develop an awareness for my physical activity. (e.g., counted steps after work, how many steps do I walk from my front door due to the main station, etc.)	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree
6.1.2*		improve my physical activity. (e.g., to take the stairs more often, to walk more often, etc.)	4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
6.1.3*		assess my physical activity. (e.g., did I walk a lot of steps, did I walk too few steps, etc.)	0. I prefer not to say.
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the function makes certain changes possible.</i>			
6.2*	Steps (wristband/application) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at my counted steps on my Fitbit tracker/application enables me to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
6.2.1*		develop an awareness for my physical activity.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree
6.2.2*		improve my physical activity.	4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
6.2.3*		assess my physical activity.	0. I prefer not to say.
6.3*	Exclusion criterion	Are you using the visual illustrations (diagrams) within the Fitbit application related to your counted steps?	Yes-no question • yes [#6.4] • no [#7]

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the visual illustrations (diagrams). This means I want to know why you are using the visual illustrations (diagrams).</i>			
6.4*	Steps visual illustrations (diagrams) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) within the Fitbit application related to my counted steps because I want to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
6.4.1*		develop an awareness for my physical activity.	
6.4.2*		improve my physical activity.	
6.4.3*		assess my physical activity.	
6.4.4*		identify and interpret differences/saliences.	
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the visual illustrations (diagrams) make certain changes possible.</i>			
6.5*	Steps visual illustrations (diagrams) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) of my counted steps within the Fitbit application enables me to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
6.5.1*		develop an awareness for my physical activity.	
6.5.2*		improve my physical activity.	
6.5.3*		assess my physical activity.	
6.5.4*		identify and interpret differences/saliences.	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Heart Rate			
7*	Exclusion criterion	Does your Fitbit activity tracker offer the possibility to track your heart rate?	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#8] • no [#9]
8*	Exclusion criterion	Are you consciously using the tracking of your heart rate with your Fitbit activity tracker? <i>Consciously means here that you are deliberately looking at your Fitbit activity tracker/application.</i>	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#8.1] • no [#9]
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the tracking of the heart rate. This means I want to know why you are using the function.</i>			
8.1*	Heart rate (wristband/application) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at my heart rate on my Fitbit tracker/application because I want to ... <i>Important: Here, diagrams are not intended.</i>	Rating scale (1-5)
8.1.1*		develop an awareness for my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising). <i>(e.g., how low/high is my heart rate during a walk, during sitting, during shopping, at work, during sports, etc.)</i>	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
8.1.2*		improve my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising). <i>(e.g., reduce my heart rate if it is too high while exercising; increase my heart rate if it is too low while exercising; I would like to reduce my all-day heart rate, etc.)</i>	0. I prefer not to say.
8.1.3*		assess my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising). <i>(e.g., to assess if my heart rate is too low or too high during a walk, while sitting, during sports.)</i>	
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the function makes certain changes possible.</i>			
8.2*	Heart rate (wristband/application) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at my heart rate on my Fitbit tracker/application enables me to ... <i>Important: Here, diagrams are not intended.</i>	Rating scale (1-5)
8.2.1*		develop an awareness for my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
8.2.2*		improve my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	0. I prefer not to say.
8.2.3*		assess my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
8.3*	Heart rate visual illustrations (diagrams)	Are you using the visual illustrations (diagrams) of the Fitbit application related to your tracked heart rate (e.g., resting heart rate, 30 days average, evaluation of workouts)?	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#8.4] • no [#8.6]
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the visual illustrations (diagrams). This means I want to know why you are using the visual illustrations (diagrams).</i>			
8.4*	Heart rate visual illustrations (diagrams) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) within the Fitbit application related to my tracked heart rate because I want to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.4.1*		develop an awareness for my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
8.4.2*		improve my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.4.3*		assess my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.4.4*		identify and interpret differences/salience.	
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the visual illustrations (diagrams) make certain changes possible.</i>			
8.5*	Heart rate visual illustrations (diagrams) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) of my tracked heart rate within the Fitbit application enables me to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.5.1*		develop an awareness for my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
8.5.2*		improve my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.5.3*		assess my heart rate (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.5.4*		identify and interpret differences/salience.	
8.6*	Heart rate zones explanation (Type 3)	Did you notice the explanation listed below within the Fitbit application? 	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#8.7 - #8.8] • no [#8.9 - #8.10]

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Users, who already knew the explanations			
<i>The already showed explanations will be shown again to answer questions related to those explanations. Please read them carefully and consciously.</i>			
8.7*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I perceive the explanations "What Are The Heart Rate Zones" ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.7.1*		easy to understand.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
8.7.2*		interesting.	
8.7.3*		not too long.	
8.7.4*		trustworthy.	
8.7.5*		not overload with information.	
8.7.6*		necessary.	
8.7.7	Further comments	If you would like to explain your decision if the explanation is/is not necessary, I would be very thankful. <i>Otherwise, you can skip this input field.</i>	[Free text field]
<i>The already shown explanations will be displayed for the last time to answer the last questions related to those explanations.</i>			
8.8*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Based on the explanation "What Are The Heart Rate Zones" ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.8.1*		I learned new things.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
8.8.2*		the technical terms and sentences are difficult to understand.	
8.8.3*		I know how to use the obtained information.	
8.8.4*		I can understand how Fitbit is calculating my heart rate data (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.8.5*		I perceive the information as sufficient and do not have any further questions on this topic.	
8.8.6*		I reflected my heart rate data (e.g., during a day, while exercising) based on the explanation. <i>(e.g., the explanation helped me to better understand my heart rate and/or in which heart rate zones I'm exercising, etc.)</i>	
8.8.7*		I adapted my exercises based on the explanation.	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Users, who saw the explanations for the first time			
<i>The already showed explanations will be shown again to answer questions related to those explanations. Please read them carefully and consciously.</i>			
8.9*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I perceive the explanations "What Are The Heart Rate Zones" ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.9.1*		easy to understand.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
8.9.2*		interesting.	
8.9.3*		not too long.	
8.9.4*		trustworthy.	
8.9.5*		not overload with information.	
8.9.6*		necessary.	
8.9.7	Further comments	If you would like to explain your decision if the explanation is/is not necessary, I would be very thankful. <i>Otherwise, you can skip this input field.</i>	[Free text field]
<i>The already shown explanations will be displayed for the last time to answer the last questions related to those explanations.</i>			
8.10*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Based on the explanation "What Are The Heart Rate Zones" ...	Rating scale (1-5)
8.10.1*		I learned new things.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
8.10.2*		the technical terms and sentences are difficult to understand.	
8.10.3*		I know how to use the obtained information.	
8.10.4*		I can understand how Fitbit is calculating my heart rate data (e.g., during a day, while exercising).	
8.10.5*		I perceive the information as sufficient and do not have any further questions on this topic.	
8.10.6*		I will reflect my heart rate data (e.g., during a day, while exercising) based on the explanation. <i>(e.g., the explanation can help me to better understand my heart rate and/or in which heart rate zones I'm exercising, etc.)</i>	
8.10.7*		I will adapt my exercises based on the explanation.	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Sleep			
9*		Does your Fitbit activity tracker offer the possibility to track your sleep?	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#10] • no [#11]
10*		Are you consciously using the sleep tracking with your Fitbit activity tracker? <i>Consciously means here that you are deliberately looking at your Fitbit activity tracker/application.</i>	Yes-no question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yes [#10.1] • no [#11]
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the sleep tracking. This means I want to know why you are using the function.</i>			
10.1*	Sleep tracking (wristband/application) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at my tracked sleep (e.g., sleep duration, sleep stages) on my Fitbit tracker/application because I want to ... VERY IMPORTANT: <i>Please consider, that the absolute sleep duration and absolute number of the different sleep stages is only visible on some Fitbit trackers (e.g., Versa). Therefore, the sleep diagrams are not intended here!</i>	Rating scale (1-5)
10.1.1*		develop an awareness for my sleep quality. (e.g., when do I go to bed, when do I wake up, do I sleep differently on days where I exercise, how long do I sleep, how long am I in which stages, etc.)	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
10.1.2*		improve my sleep quality. (e.g., I would like to go to bed earlier, I would like to sleep longer, I would like to change specific sleep behavior habits, etc.)	0. I prefer not to say.
10.1.3*		assess my sleep quality. (e.g., I would like to assess if it was a “good” sleep or a “bad” sleep.)	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the function makes certain changes possible.</i>			
10.2*	Sleep tracking (wristband/application) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at my tracked sleep (e.g., sleep duration, sleep stages) on my Fitbit tracker/application enables me to ... <i>VERY IMPORTANT: Please consider, that the absolute sleep duration and absolute number of the different sleep stages is only visible on some Fitbit trackers (e.g., Versa). Therefore, the sleep diagrams are not intended here!</i>	Rating scale (1-5)
10.2.1*		develop an awareness for my sleep quality.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
10.2.2*	improve my sleep quality.		
10.2.3*	assess my sleep quality.		
10.3*	Sleep tracking visual illustrations (diagrams)	Are you using the visual illustrations (diagrams) of the Fitbit application related to your tracked sleep (e.g., 30 days average, comparison, daily sleep records)?	Yes-no question • yes [#10.4] • no [#10.6]
<i>Please note that the following page is about your expectation regarding the visual illustrations (diagrams). This means I want to know why you are using the visual illustration (diagrams).</i>			
10.4*	Sleep tracking visual illustrations (diagrams) expectation	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I'm looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) within the Fitbit application related to my tracked sleep because I want to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
10.4.1*		develop an awareness for my sleep quality.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
10.4.2*	improve my sleep quality.		
10.4.3*	assess my sleep quality.		
10.4.4*	identify and interpret differences/saliencees.		

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
<i>Please note that the next page is no longer about your expectation (!) but about your experience. This means that I would like to know to what extent the visual illustrations (diagrams) make certain changes possible.</i>			
10.5*	Sleep tracking visual illustrations (diagrams) experience	Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Looking at the visual illustrations (diagrams) within the Fitbit application related to my tracked sleep enables me to ...	Rating scale (1-5)
10.5.1*		develop an awareness for my sleep quality.	1. Strongly Disagree
10.5.2*		improve my sleep quality.	2. Disagree
10.5.3*		assess my sleep quality.	3. Neither Agree nor Disagree
10.5.4*		identify and interpret differences/salience.	4. Agree
			5. Strongly Agree
			0. I prefer not to say.

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
<i>The following items [#10.6 - #10.10] are only shown if a participant said 'yes' regarding the question if the activity tracker offers heart tracking [#7]</i>			
10.6*	Sleep stages' characteristics explanation (Type 3)	<p>Did you notice the explanation listed below or similar explanations (1,2,3,4,5) within the Fitbit application?</p> <p><i>The 1st sentence of the explanations (2,3,4,5) always corresponds to your individually recorded duration.</i></p>	<p>Yes-no question</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> yes [#10.7 - #10.8] no [#10.9 - #10.10]

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Users, who already knew the explanations			
<i>The already showed explanations will be shown again to answer questions related to those explanations. Please read them carefully and consciously.</i>			
10.7*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you:	Rating scale (1-5)
10.7.1*		I perceive the explanations (1,2,3,4,5) above ...	
10.7.2*		easy to understand.	1. Strongly Disagree
10.7.3*		interesting.	2. Disagree
10.7.4*		not too long.	3. Neither Agree nor Disagree
10.7.5*		trustworthy.	4. Agree
10.7.6*		not overload with information.	5. Strongly Agree
10.7.6*		necessary.	0. I prefer not to say.
10.7.7	Further comments	If you would like to explain your decision if the explanation is/is not necessary, I would be very thankful. <i>Otherwise, you can skip this input field.</i>	[Free text field]
<i>The already shown explanations will be displayed for the last time to answer the last questions related to those explanations.</i>			
10.8*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you:	Rating scale (1-5)
10.8.1*		Based on the explanations (1,2,3,4,5) above ...	
10.8.2*		I learned new things.	1. Strongly Disagree
10.8.3*		the technical terms and sentences are difficult to understand.	2. Disagree
10.8.4*		I know how to use the obtained information.	3. Neither Agree nor Disagree
10.8.5*		I can understand how Fitbit is illustrating/calculating my tracked sleep.	4. Agree
10.8.6*		I perceive the information as sufficient and do not have any further questions on this topic.	5. Strongly Agree
10.8.7*		I reflected my tracked sleep based on the explanation. (e.g., the explanation helps me to better understand my tracked sleep and/or to identify where optimization is needed.)	0. I prefer not to say.
10.8.7*		I adapted my sleep behavior based on the explanation.	

Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Users, who saw the explanations for the first time			
<i>The already showed explanations will be shown again to answer questions related to those explanations. Please read them carefully and consciously.</i>			
10.9*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: I perceive the explanations (1,2,3,4,5) above ...	Rating scale (1-5)
10.9.1*		easy to understand.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
10.9.2*		interesting.	
10.9.3*		not too long.	
10.9.4*		trustworthy.	
10.9.5*		not overload with information.	
10.9.6*		necessary.	
10.9.7	Further comments	If you would like to explain your decision if the explanation is/is not necessary, I would be very thankful. <i>Otherwise, you can skip this input field.</i>	[Free text field]
<i>The already shown explanations will be displayed for the last time to answer the last questions related to those explanations.</i>			
10.10*		Please evaluate if the following statements apply to you: Based on the explanations (1,2,3,4,5) above ...	Rating scale (1-5)
10.10.1*		I learned new things.	1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neither Agree nor Disagree 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree 0. I prefer not to say.
10.10.2*		the technical terms and sentences are difficult to understand.	
10.10.3*		I know how to use the obtained information.	
10.10.4*		I can understand how Fitbit is illustrating/calculating my tracked sleep.	
10.10.5*		I perceive the information as sufficient and do not have any further questions on this topic.	
10.10.6*		I will reflect my tracked sleep based on the explanation. (e.g., the explanation can help me to better understand my tracked sleep and/or to identify where optimization is needed.)	
10.10.7*		I will adapt my sleep behavior based on the explanation.	

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Items (#) marked with * characterize questions/statements which were obligatory.

#	Subject	Question	Answer Type
Background Questions			
<i>Finally, I would like to ask some background questions (such as gender, age) to identify possible differences.</i>			
11*	Gender	Please indicate your gender:	Single selection <ul style="list-style-type: none">• female• male• I prefer not to say.• Other: [Free text field]
12*	Year of birth	Please indicate your year of birth:	Single selection [before 1920] [1920, 1921...2006] [after 2006]
13	Remarks, Suggestions & Questions	Here, you have the possibility to write down your remarks, suggestions or questions:	[Free text field]